

IN THE PROCESS OF PREPARING STUDENTS FOR FAMILY LIFE PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT, EDUCATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF HYGIENE CULTURE DEVELOPMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8171120>

Abstract: the content of the pedagogical process aimed at the development of hygienic culture in students is to show the place of hygienic culture in the system of family relationships, intellectual potential, the importance of globalization and, most importantly, to show that its adherence is a product of the process of people's struggle for survival and changes in their lives, thereby strengthening the students' views on the high importance of hygienic culture in the formation of a healthy life.

Key words: hygienic culture, higher education, healthy lifestyle, religion, preventive measure, ethics

Today, the task of preparing students for family life along with education of students as high-potential personnel is gaining importance. Because many young people who have started an independent family life are not able to accept responsibility, take on new tasks and other changes, and in general, they are not sufficiently prepared for family life. This is reflected in the devaluation of oriental family values, disputes, family conflicts, and gender problems related to inequality. At the same time, it is possible to see that in the new family life, based on the lack of hygienic culture, there is an increase in the number of negative situations related to the birth of defective children and hygienic diseases.

That is why the issues of forming a hygienic culture among young people and preparing them for family life on this basis are gaining priority. For this, it is necessary to bring work with young people to a new level, communicate with them correctly and effectively, and modernize the work system. Through this, it is aimed to implement preventive, formal and educational reforms aimed at directing them to various fields, entering into social relations and finding their place in society.

In this process, taking into account the fact that some of the young people who are on the threshold of family life are studying in higher education, and the main organized layer are students, the issues of preparing students for family life in higher education and forming a hygienic culture in them are gaining relevance. This creates the need to improve the effectiveness of preparing students for family life, to bring work with students to a new level.

For this, first of all, it is necessary to form a hygienic culture in students, to protect their health, and to develop the skills of following a healthy lifestyle. Therefore, it is important to improve the pedagogical system of developing hygienic culture in students in higher education, and to introduce new approaches to it.

Improving the educational program aimed at the development of hygienic culture, introducing it into the pedagogical process based on a new approach is an important methodological basis for understanding social life, the rational attitude of man to the

environment, the "nature-society-man" system, making theoretical conclusions and practical recommendations for the formation of a healthy lifestyle.

Characterization of hygienic culture as an objective, necessary integral social-cultural phenomenon in the modernized pedagogical process serves to scientifically determine the main factors of creating a healthy lifestyle and the interrelationship of hygiene and culture. One of the important tasks in higher pedagogical education is to emphasize to students that hygienic culture is an integral part of culture, and it is also an activity aimed at creating a comfortable and healthy environment for the body of people in natural living conditions.

In general, any social relationship in society inevitably goes back to the relationship of a person with nature, that is, the relationship between "man and man", "man and society" - the biological existence of nature manifested as a human phenomenon. is also a relationship. Therefore, the separation of "pure social relations" from ecological relations has an artificial, mechanistic character. According to its content, social relations consist of direct connections between nature and them in the form of interactions between individuals and social units, which are its subjects, that is, "social relations are the manifestation of all social relations at the level of an individual" [1] . However, the interpretation of activity and responsibility in environmental relations at the level of the individual does not undermine its social essence.

It is also necessary to improve the pedagogical process aimed at the development of hygienic culture in higher education, to establish educational integration, and in the case of interdisciplinary cooperation, to inculcate the fact that hygienic culture is unique in each period chronologically, geographically, legally, religiously, and functionally. In the emergence and chronological development of hygiene, it is necessary to show that it has gradually become a cultural reflection of human social life, a daily necessity in the creation of material and spiritual wealth from ancient times to the present. It is also appropriate to approach hygienic culture based on the influence of ethno-demographic factors, to study in connection with natural living conditions, and to form students' attitudes in this regard.

In higher education, it is useful to use the educational importance of religious studies in the improvement of the system aimed at the development of hygienic culture in the preparation of students for the university life, to include the relations of various religions in the society regarding the importance of hygienic culture in family life. In particular, it will be effective to explain the beneficial aspects of the formation of hygienic culture in Islam, and the giving of attitudes in this regard. The connection of hygienic culture with religion is that in the history of mankind, any religion ensured its existence and strengthened its position among the masses through the education of hygienic culture.

It is also effective to provide information about the activities of the Ministry of Family and Neighborhood Support, its tasks, effectiveness, achieved results, and the principles of their work, to enter into dialogue with them, and to regularly provide information about the possibilities and ways of receiving help in preparing young people for family life, developing a hygienic culture in them. In our opinion, the existing management apparatus and institutional system in the society will serve the development of hygienic culture, it will depend on ensuring the functional harmony of the family, neighborhood, educational institutions and state organizations. For this, it is necessary to pay special attention to the following tasks:

- first, taking into account the law of organic connection between man and nature, focusing on forming a hygienic attitude to it;

- secondly, to study the development of the youth's spirituality and mentality in relation to the ecological and hygienic conditions of the environment;

- thirdly, promotion of hygienic views among the general public in the formation of a culture of human knowledge of the laws of nature, rational use of its resources;

-fourthly, further development of the current educational methodology aimed at the development of hygienic culture, taking into account national and cultural characteristics in the continuation of its new program directions;

- fifthly, it is important to recognize alternative views of hygienic culture among students, to enrich them and to harmonize modern scientific achievements, social hygiene, sanitary service culture.

In general, state-level preventive measures aimed at the development of hygienic culture are aimed at the following: first, protection and normalization of the natural environment on the basis of sanitary-hygiene students; secondly, to further improve the sanitary-hygienic condition of the population's living conditions, household lifestyle, in particular, food culture; thirdly, development of projects related to the development of labor hygiene in material production; fourth, taking measures to improve the hygienic basis of working conditions in agriculture; fifth, to improve the hygiene of rural living conditions to a highly urbanized level; sixth, finding solutions related to reducing the level of dangerous infectious, cardiovascular and other diseases of hygiene; seventh, it shows its importance by increasing the role of hygienic culture in the formation of the philosophy of a healthy lifestyle.

Today, the tasks of improving environmental education in higher education are becoming more urgent. This is also caused by the hygienic problems of the society. That is why it is required to enlighten, teach and explain the issues of forming a relationship to global environmental problems, forming a rational relationship with nature, and protecting the environment based on new approaches. In the 21st century, the biosphere balance of our planet has been threatened to such an extent that if the world community does not take measures related to the integration of ecological and hygienic culture that ensures harmony between man and nature, it became clear that the danger of ecohygienic destruction not only for humanity, but also for the whole being is real. In such a situation, the need to create organizational and theoretical foundations for the promotion of hygienic culture for the protection of human health is increasing. This creates the tasks of forming a hygienic culture and teaching in harmony with environmental responsibility. Therefore, in today's higher education, it is necessary to provide a sequence of subjects that can be mutually integrated and create interdisciplinary cooperation in the formation of the system of subjects and the sequence of teaching.

Religious values are also important in the development of hygienic culture. In general, it concerns goodness according to its national, especially religious content. Religious hygienic values were honored by our ancestors and served to strengthen the place and position of religion in society as a special form of social consciousness. Today, the approach to human life based on hygienic culture requires a new attitude to people's rights and freedoms. Because people can determine their daily life needs based on the norms of hygienic culture. In this, the hygienic right is the internal legal order of creating a healthy lifestyle in human life, which gives the freedom to keep the universe tidy. That is, if the main factor of human activity is determined by hygienic and ecological culture, it is implemented by state authorities and organizations that manage and regulate the people. Hygienic right - organizes, manages and

controls the hygienic activities of society members without exceeding the norm and without contradicting other legal procedures. We have shown in detail the organization of the most relevant principle of national ideology - renewal of society based on spiritual values. According to this principle, it is justified that the national ideology is the priority direction of the state policy in solving the socio-spiritual and moral issues of the development of culture in general, and hygienic culture in particular. The ideological task of hygienic culture is to improve the health of society members and the environment, to inculcate the national policy of the state in people's minds and practical activities, and it embodies the ideas of internal and external policy of its development. After all, environmental protection, creating a healthy lifestyle is the main duty of the ideology, and it organizes various programs, theoretical and practical work in accordance with the purpose.

Ethical factors play an important role in hygienic culture. After all, environmental pollution, which has a negative effect on human health, is also associated with immoral phenomena such as smoking, alcoholism, and drug addiction. Today, the role of forming a hygienic culture among the population, especially young people, is incomparable. It should also remain the primary method for the widespread prevention of AIDS, the plague of the 21st century. The improvement of specific methods and means of forming a hygienic culture in people's minds has been widely analyzed. Issues of strengthening the role of hygienic culture textbooks, visual aids, national traditions, and modern pedagogical technologies in teaching the public to a healthy lifestyle are highlighted. Also, didactic and promotional methods in the development of hygienic culture were described, and their content and functional importance were revealed: first, to expand the possibilities of using religious values in the development of hygienic culture; secondly, to strengthen the primacy and legal basis of the hygienic right in ensuring human freedoms; thirdly, to introduce spiritual, ideological, spiritual and moral principles of hygienic culture development into social life; fourthly, improvement of pedagogic-didactic, promotion-propaganda methods in the development of hygienic culture based on new innovative technologies; fifth, to organize special columns on hygienic culture in mass media; sixth, to strengthen the methodological foundations of the integration of institutions responsible for the development of hygienic culture.

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